

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B137
Date: 30 Sep 2005
Take Off: 08:51:36
Landing: 13:51:49
Flight Time: 5h0013m

Campaign: CLOPAP
Operating Area: London Plume evolution – off East Anglia coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	CCN (training)	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	WAS	Jim Hopkins	York University
9	AMS	James Allan	University of Manchester
10	NOxy / peroxide / filters	Dave Stewart	UEA
11	PTRMS	Jennifer Murphy	UEA
12	CVI / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
13	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
14			
15			
16			

Flight Track:

B137 Track 30-SEP-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b137
 Date: 30 Sep 05
 Project: CLOPAP
 Location: East Anglia Coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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083803		engine start	0.26 kft	126	
084121		power change	0.26 kft	126	
084401		taxy start	0.26 kft	075	
085136		T/O	0.25 kft	212	from cranfield
085950		noxy cal run	10.0 kft	060	
090032		asp open	10.0 kft	060	
092049	092438	Profile 1	4.9 - 1.2 kft	176	
092600	093743	Run 1	1.2 kft	179	
093948	095218	Run 2	2.3 kft	292	
095549	100313	Run 3	2.3 kft	121	
100314	100453	Profile 2	2.3 - 1.2 kft	144	
100453	101317	Run 4	1.2 kft	147	
101518	102231	Run 5	1.2 - 1.3 kft	339	
102231	102342	Profile 3	1.3 - 2.4 kft	316	
102342	103507	Run 6	2.4 - 2.3 kft	318	
103803	104506	Run 7	2.3 kft	157	
104506	104648	Profile 4	2.3 - 1.2 kft	143	
104648	105050	Run 8	1.2 kft	145	
105152	105617	Run 9	1.3 kft	038	
105618	105733	Profile 5	1.3 - 2.3 kft	326	
105733	110809	Run 10	2.3 kft	313	
111120	111458	Run 11	1.9 kft	145	
111458	111541	Profile 6	1.9 - 1.4 kft	146	
111542	112314	Run 12	1.4 kft	146	
112416	112830	Run 13	1.4 kft	041	
112830	115138	Run 14	1.4 kft	314	
115330	120037	Run 15	1.0 kft	123	
120124	121422	Run 16	1.3 - 1.2 kft	137	
121512	123830	Run 17	1.2 kft	231	
124035	124230	Run 18	1.2 kft	047	
124414	125621	Run 19	2.3 - 2.2 kft	003	
125713	130059	Run 20	2.2 kft	042	
130156	131256	Run 21	2.2 kft	133	
131901		noxy calcs	10.0 kft	322	
134453		asp closed	2.4 kft	265	
135149		Land	0.27 kft	212	at Cranfield
135516		standstill	0.29 kft	309	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B137 Track 30-SEP-05

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 9 (prepared by K.N. Bower)

Flight Number : B137

Date: Friday 30th September 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

CLOPAP Sortie Aims:

To study the evolution of aerosol in an urban plume as it advects away from the source. To investigate the interaction of the aerosol and gases with cloud both as the aerosol/gas modifies the cloud microphysics/chemistry and the cloud modifies the aerosol and gases.

CLOPAP Sortie Location:

The plan is to fly in an area of low cloud and sample pollution from the London region as it advects north eastwards and interacts with the cloud layer. For this flight where we expect a SW wind to take the plume over East Anglia and the North sea (to the north and east of East Anglia), several sets of cross-wind runs of 12 minutes duration (or of half this duration on reciprocal headings if close into the pollution source over land) will be attempted at various altitudes in the time available. Low cloud is only currently forecasted over the Thames Estuary, East Anglia and North Sea (ECMWF). However, whether cloud is present over land or not a first set* of crosswind legs close to the source area (as along the A-B leg of B131) is desirable.

CLOPAP Sortie Summary:

The case studies will be carried out by flying a series of transects across the plume within the boundary layer (one below cloud, and at least one in cloud) and one in the lower free troposphere immediately above cloud top. Each of these sets of transects may be immediately preceded by a vertical profile (where possible) extending into the lower free troposphere starting from as close to the surface as possible. These profiles will establish the vertical mixing and structure of the sampled air and establish the optimum altitudes for the following transects. This flight pattern will be repeated at intervals of about 25km[#] separation. Current plans allow for up to four sets of runs to be carried out in 4 out of 5 positions, each set consisting of up to four (but generally three) cross wind runs. Profiles will be carried out where possible in each or in chosen sets of runs.

Although we are not aiming to perform a comprehensive Lagrangian study, this flight plan will allow us to approximately track the same air as it is advected downwind of the source region. Runs at each altitude may be cut down to a minimum total length of up to 12 minutes (or 84km) duration or omitted, or certain profiles sacrificed in order to achieve the required study of plume evolution and interaction with cloud. Details of the number of cross wind legs and altitudes of these may be adjusted by the mission scientist during the flight to best achieve the science goals in the conditions encountered.

*In the absence of cloud over land, fewer boundary layer transects will be performed, ie the “in-cloud” leg, some profiles and/or above BL legs will be omitted, or a whole set of legs omitted in order to carry out more sets of runs in cloud covered areas (and hence to improve detection of plume evolution) in the operational area.

CLOPAP Sortie Detail: PTO

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 9 (draft 1 : prepared by K.N. Bower)

Flight Number : B137

Date: Friday 30th September 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

CLOPAP Sortie Detail:

1. Take off and climb to FL 100 for transit at cruise speed to operating area (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent carrying out NO_x calibration at that level)
2. When downwind of chosen urban source, descend to minimum safe altitude below cloud. Perform a profile ascent by climbing at 1000 ft per minute to pass through cloud and to an altitude 200 ft above cloud top/ boundary layer top (NB. The initial profile may be carried out as a descent from above BL or cloud top to below cloud base level if safe to do so).
3. Descend to below cloud base, proceed across wind in the boundary layer until outside the plume as detected by CN counter/gases. Mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect. Perform a straight and level run (SLR) below cloud base (200 ft below cloud base) across wind and of total length 84 km[#]. CCN measurements should commence at the start of this run. Core Chemistry calibrations should be carried out at start of run (as required) and completion announced so that WAS sampling can begin.
4. Ascend to the middle of the cloud layer. Turn through 180 degrees. Mission Scientist to announce in cloud transect (AMS to switch to CVI inlet) and perform SLR of length 84 km[#].
5. Ascend to 200 feet above cloud top turn through 180 degrees - mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect (AMS to return to Rosemount inlet). Perform a SLR of length 84 km[#]. CCN measurements should also commence at the start of this run. In the event that we cannot operate above cloud top a second in-cloud run will be carried out at a higher altitude than in 4.
6. Ascend to cruising altitude to transit to 25[#] km downwind and repeat steps 2 to 6
7. Continue repetitions until available flight time in science area is exhausted
8. Climb to transit level to return to home base (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent at FL100 for NO_x calibration)

NB. In the absence of cloud over land:

9. In the absence of cloud over land steps 3 and 4 will be replaced by a single in boundary layer cross-wind transect. Items 2 and 5 may also be omitted as considered appropriate by the mission scientist. If cloud is only present in a limited region a whole set of cross wind legs may be omitted to concentrate on investigations with the cloud covered region

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 9 (Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud) : TWC/KNB

CLOPAP Scientific Aims

1. To investigate the evolution of an urban plume as it is advected away from the source in cloudy conditions (if low cloud in this area)[#]. Changes in chemical speciation and the partitioning of species between the gas and particulate phases will be investigated.
2. To measure the changes in the size distribution and Cloud Condensation Nucleus (CCN) activity spectrum of the aerosol.
3. To measure changes in cloud microphysics as the aerosol properties in the plume, particularly those of the sub-set of aerosol acting as CCN.
4. To investigate the differences in the composition of aerosol that form cloud droplets and those that remain unactivated and interstitial to the cloud, and to observe how this changes as the plume ages.
5. To investigate the role of vertical exchange between the boundary layer and the free troposphere to understand its effect on the transport of aerosols and trace gases on the cloudy plume.

CLOPAP Weather Conditions

Ideally, a stratocumulus capped boundary layer forming over the land and sea downwind of a main source of urban air pollution. Limited convective penetration of the boundary layer top is acceptable (but not deep convection). The cloud cover should exceed 70% in the study areas.

CLOPAP Key Measurements requiring operator intervention during flight

Cloud Physics

- **FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP**, Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high/low concentrations,
- **ADA and CPI** – as above
- **CCN** - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample and spectrum per run, if possible.
- **J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC**. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- **TWC** – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

Chemistry Measurements

WAS - 2 bottle samples[#] per 84km flight leg in BL unless otherwise notified by the Mission Scientist (first sample to be collected after core chemistry calibrations are completed), 1 in above cloud/BL legs.

NO_x, Ozone, SO₂, CO, PTRMS, Hydrogen peroxide to operate continuously.

AMS - to be operated on **Rosemount inlet** out of cloud, **CVI** inlet in cloud. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed or after take-off. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight or before landing.

Filters – these should be exposed on boundary layer out of cloud runs only.

Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rearward facing.

CCN measurements :alleviator should be filled at the start of cloud free passes.

Bottle filling and filter sampling should occur in clear air transects only. Two[#] bottle samples should be filled during each boundary layer transect and 1 during the free troposphere transect. The Mission scientist will indicate when in plume using CN and selected gas measurements. All other instruments should run continuously. (# adjusted as appropriate for number of available bottles)

Mission Scientist's Log

MSC1 K. BOWER

CLOPAP 9

Flight No **B.137**.....

Date **30/09/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
9:51:42	BS7				T/O
					CB ~ 800' CT ~ 2100'
9:53:25	BS7	2500			
9:54:55	BS7	5000			
9:59:25	NO _{2y}	FL100	60	52.3N/0.1W	NO _{2y} cal 18 m/s / 292° 3.9°C / 0.52°C 895 mb time check
9:08:50	GMT E	10:08:56		BS7 (ICNS)	
9:11:25					Some Cloud Tops below - maybe 1000'
9:16:30		FL100		52.8/1.8E	At point 30 - turning Southwards
9:16:39	NO _{2y}				NO _{2y} cal done
9:16:04	descent				
9:20:49	PI	FL50 -	176	52.4N/1.9E	
9:21:35	PI	4200		52.4/1.9E	12.91 / 10.06 11 m/s / 258 865
9:23:05	PI	2700	179	52.3/1.9E	2700 CT
9:24:32	PI and	1300	128	52.2/2.0E	969 mb 11.79 / 12.95° 14 m/s / 253° 970
9:25:53	RI	1300	179		NO _{2y} saw elevated NO ₂ - dropping
9:27:10	RI		180	52.1/2.0	AMS in CVI CPC - 2000 cm ⁻³ CVI CN = 2000 cm ⁻³
9:29:12	RI				1500 cm ⁻³ CPC
9:30:00	RI	1300	197	51.9/1.9E	One more cuts done CØ been playing up - several adjustments
9:37:37					larger water drop conc dropped.
9:37:42	RI and	1310.	222	51.5/1.6E	12.3 / 13.5° 13 m/s / 246° 969 mb 2200 m/s
9:38:25					Climbing to 2400' (on 1010 mb)
		2350			Brighter

Mission Scientist's Log

M. SCI KETH BOWER

CLOAP 9

Flight No **B.137**.....

Date **30/01/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:39:46	R2	2400	293	51.6/1.4	12.05' / 12.9 930m 11m/s / 263° 2 CPC 200 cm ⁻² (0.01 on a CVI)
9:42:50	R2	2400		51.7/	near CT - sunshine Photos on ZDC 25-100
9:44:18	R2	2400			Right in CT - Cloud Free
9:44:57	R2	2400	317	51.8/1.1	in CT again
9:45:30	R2				Cloud Free ^{sun} - CEN section
9:47:04	R2	2400	317	51.9/1.0	Back in Cloud - NO ₂ reading but a min earlier - starting to rise again
09:51:00					Cloud free for some time now - Broken cloud layer above.
9:52:17	R2 and	2400	317	52.1/0.7	.
9:53:00		2400			Photo RMS in LMT
9:53:25		2400			Photo LMS - above cloud
9:54:09					Photo RMS - above cloud
					Photo LMS - looking v
9:55:48	R3 ↓	2400	133	52.1/0.7	13m/s / 260° 930m 15.7/14.64
9:58:20	R3	2400	133	52.0/0.8	looks to be cloud free - AMS → around
9:58:55	R3	2400	142	51.9/0.9	AMS back on Rose and
10:00:35	R3			51.9/1.0	CT's - CPC - less than 100 - Spike in CPC to 1000 at CT
10:03:08	R3 and R2 ↓		145	51.7/1.2	CO started rising before dawn AMS → CVI
					NO ₂ ↑ CO
10:09:45	R2 and R4	1300	146	51.6/1.3E	AMS on CVI now.

Mission Scientist's Log

M. SCI ICEMTH BOWER

CUOPAD 9

Flight No **B.137**.....

Date **30/01/08**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:06:28	R4	1300	147	51.6/1.4E	300 cm ⁻³ CRC - Measurable levels
10:09:17					200-400 nm particles - really clean TDF
10:09:45	R4	1300	147	51.4/1.6	CO out low.
10:13:16	R4 end	1300		51.2/1.7E	
10:15:15	R5	1300	343	51.3/1.9E	11.79/13.64° 15m/s/208° 965mb
10:16:10	R5	1300	0	51.4/1.9E	
10:22:30	R5 end / P3	1300	317	51.8/1.8E	965mb climbing to 2400
10:23:34	P3 end / R6	2400	316	51.8/1.7	at point C to D. CO out.
10:27:10					Bright
					FSSP - crashed at end of run 5 - too many particles
10:27:54					mut conc PSSP, small drizzle drops
10:28:20					CVI N ² conc decrease
	R6	2400		52.0/1.4	Out of cloud - CCN sample
10:32:25	R6				AMS on Rosemount
10:33:33	R6		317	52.2/1.1	15.19/14.08° 6/274° 930mb
10:35:04	R6 end	2400		52.3/1.0	Will return at same level - then down over cloud E 1400
10:38:01	R7	2400	153	52.3/1.0	D → C.
10:38:50	R7	2400	141	52.3/1.1E	Photo N ² S - at ^{working} T
10:45:09	R7 end / P4	2400	144	52.0/1.5E	descending
10:45:50	P4				AMS on CVI - hitting CT's
10:46:07	P4	1700'	144	51.9/1.5	in cloud
10:46:46	R4 end / R5	1300	145	51.9/1.6	13m/s/249° 12.9/14.08 965mb 217
					AMS - strong signals off CVI

Mission Scientist's Log

M.SCI KEITH BOWER

CLOPP 9

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Date **30/09/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:46:04	R8	1300	146	51.8/1.7E	NO ₂ shd w CN inc too, SO ₂ too
10:50:48	R8 end	1300		51.7/1.7	AMS dirty particle - high SF
10:50:52	R9		35		plastic SO ₂ - odd bit NO ₂ 'big' at 44
					hit this plume and time we drop down and
					exit - main plume is over land
10:56:13	R9 on / Pst	1300	318	52.0/2.2E	E/F cut point E
					NO ₂ , SO ₂ , CN ↑ at end R9
10:57:31	P5 end / R10	2400	316	52.0/2.1	
10:59:55	R10	2400	319	52.1/2.0	Running along CT's NO ₂ ↓ SO ₂ ↓ CN ↑
11:01:50	R10	2400	318		Above CT. now - AMS → Rosemount
11:02:28	R10	2400	319	52.3/1.5E	AMS on Rose - PTRMS - seeing more HC
					above CT.
					not prof
					(Will drop down to 1800' on QNH 1011
					on receipt after end of this run)
11:02:07	R10 end			52.5/1.5E	
11:09:10		1800'		52.6/1.5E	AMS on CVI at
11:11:18	R11	1800'	152	52.5/1.5E	F → F 17 m/s / 280°
11:12:15	R11				NO ₂ just picking up, CN - in cloud
11:12:20	R11		144	52.5/1.6E	Out of cloud
					Cenccs drizzle drops > 100µm
11:14:15	R11				AMS - v white - mainly cencc ↑ above CT.
11:14:57	R11 on / P6	1800'	146	52.3/1.7E	Particle descent
11:15:40	P6 end / R12	1300	145	52.3/1.8E	NO ₂ - shaking up (T _{co} + NO ₂)
					CN high again SO ₂ slight in
				52.2/1.9.	AMS - CVI once more Dry / 1 hrs

Mission Scientist's Log

M.SCI KEITH BOWER

CLOPAP 9

Flight No **B.137**.....

Date **30/09/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:23:11	R12cont	1300	146	52.0/22	13m/s/244° 964mb 12.54/14.02 at E
11:24:13	R13	1300	38	52.0/24	E → G still in cloud - SO ₂ high ~ 0.5, NO _x low ~ 50nb. (rechecked at post)
11:28:15	R13	1300	329	52.2/2.5	G - M Wt hand turn at G.
11:29:30	R14				Solt change.
11:31:20					NO _x ↑ again (NO ₂ has maintained high level)
11:42:13	R14	1300	320		NO ₂ dropping now, SO ₂ gone down
11:45:08			318	52.4/23	In a gap between layers - CN1 cond dropped CB ~ low ~ 100ft - hole on AMS some sea str.
					NO ₂ SO ₂ CN & out of cloud ↑ in CT.
11:39:40	R14	1300			Rain around here. near M.
11:40:05		1300	312	52.8/18E	Out of cloud & pollution clear - burning 6m/s/284° (ATC 273°)
11:44:35					after near CT - rain
11:45:50	R14	1300	286	53.0/1.4	Slight LH7 - for a while - landing around N coast East Angle 7m/s/285° 963mb 15.99/16.07
					DTAMS - more inlets in above BL leg.
					Smokes N found 87 Blackness part.
					No cloud below - just sea - but pollution is low
					AMS need to be removed etc.

Mission Scientist's Log

M. SCI KEITH BOWER

CLODAP 9

Flight No **B.137**.....

Date **30/09/03**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:51:37	R14 end			53.1/0.9	QNH 1015
11:53:07		1000'			turns - wheels down
11:53:29	R15	1000'	124	53.1/1.0E	turns then desc. 976mb (heading to H)
	R15	1000	128	53.1/1.1	Winds / 249° 976mb NO _x Spkt
					CN 2640 cm ⁻³ SO ₂ 0.7 ppb
					CO cal done
11:57:28	R15	1000	128	52.9/1.3E	Photo R15 - now raining heavily
11:59:13	R15 5m				Left turn ATC - cloud below
					2 fuel jts
12:00:25					Rt turn.
12:00:55	R15 end	1000	131	52.9/1.8	(AMS to change) CO, NO _x just rose a bit
12:01:21	R16	1300	137	52.8/1.6	AMS on CVI, NO _x still high SO ₂
					dropped alt., CN increasing 5000
					Rain on screen.
12:02:43	R16	1300	131	52.8/1.34	CN now increasing - approaching H
12:04:04				52.7/1.9	past H.
12:06:00	R16	1300.	144	52.6/	much brighter here
					400 OPC - meteorological chem on AM
					miss / my miss.
12:10:15	R16	1300	148	52.4/2.2	Gap in cloud
					CCN sample - in time - back in desc
					CO, NO _x etc correlated with cloud / BL.
					NO _x CO rising again
12:12:43	R16.				AMS - see now still on records
12:14:18	R16 end	13000	178	52.2/2.5	At Golb. turns R17.

Mission Scientist's Log

M.SCI KEITH BOWER

CLOPAPA

Flight No **B.137**.....

Date **30/09/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:15:11	R17	1300	228	52.2/2.4	G → E
12:20:40	R17				AMS - getting lot of stuff on CVI - drop out PCASP - 500 - affected by drops.
12:21:45	R17	1300	230	52.0/2.0	Much less thru CVI now than 5 mins ago NO _x shooting up 11 parts SO ₂ did peak
12:22:51	R17			51.9/2.0	now low. CN has peaked now low.
12:26:45	R17	1300	229	51.8/1.7	top of C → A
12:29:30	R17				High NO _x 14 parts - now dropping CN increasing, SO ₂ NO _x high
12:31:38					detectable O ₃ - not enough to see with PTAMS - now actually alt high
12:32:55	R17	1300	-	51.8/1.3	part A NO _x , SO ₂ going high
12:35:40			237	51.5/1.2	CO, NO _x falling now AMS - SO ₂ ↑ and now dominant feature as leg progressed NO _x dropping right down
12:38:31					SO ₂ NO _x ↑ again CO leveled
12:39:14					NO _x higher 19.71 parts
12:39:55				51.4/1.0E	21 parts Now (21.9 peak) changed NO ₂ -
12:40:35	R18	1300			going back to A. NO _x 23
12:42:30	R18 cont	1300		51.5/1.2	changing to go to 2300' for com wind by B →
					2150 - 2200 - above CT.

Mission Scientist's Log

MSCI - KEITH BOWER

CLOP 9

Flight No **B.137**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:43:50					AMS on Rosemount
12:44:12	R19st	2300'			approaching A - CN to do
12:46:04	R19	2300	340	51.6/1.3	
					AMS CPC seeing back of CPC particles again (odd large droplets?)
12:52:55	R19				3 plates LHS, AMS front - at about CT
12:54:40	R19	2300	316	52.0/0.8E	Photo LHS 7m/s/262° 933mb 17.5°/15.32°C
12:56:20	R19cont	2300	316	52.1/0.7E	moving B-D now
12:57:13	R20st	2300	40	52.1/0.7	B-D transit
					Broken Cloud - RHS, LHS below - see ground
					CNC - spike 30,000 - (PC saw it too)
13:00:57	R20cont	2300		52.3/1.0E	(NO _{2x} saw small spike).
13:01:55	R21st	2300	134	52.3/1.0E	D→C
					AMS down track SO ₄ - Nucleation
13:12:54	R21cont	2300	143	51.8/1.7E	
13:17:06	trans	8000	319	51.9/1.6E	CNC soaking - CPC too - rain
13:17:26			318	52.0/1.6	climbing to FL100
		9700		52.0/1.5	in cloud - CT's
13:18:59	NO _{2c}	FL100	321	52.1/1.5	NO _{2x} calcs
13:35:18	NO _{2xy}	FL100	247	52.5/0.3E	Calcs complete
14:38:53	BST	descent			
					(CB ~ 6000ft ish) CT 1700
					230/7ms CF 1100 ± haze
14:57:51	BST				land.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B137

Date : 30 Sep 2005

Operator and contact info : Doug Anderson (dougan@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	Inst not up to temp until after take off. Initial few calcs poor due to cal gas flow too low. Sorted before first run.
O₃	None
NO_x	None
SO₂	None
TDLAS	Not fitted
WAS	None notified

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
Shorter (quick calcs) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
09:12:13	FL100	Initial try 'bad'. Second worked but sensitivity was very low due to cal gas being off or very low pressure.
09:17:32	FL100	Better but still low sensitivity
09:28:49	1300'	still low sensitivity
09:37:01	1300'	sensitivity OK now
09:43:05	2400'	
10:09:24	1200'	
10:09:24	1200'	
10:26:54	2400'	
10:49:53	1300'	
11:00:40	2400'	
11:11:05- 11:11:45	2400'	Quick cal OK, no full cal required
11:15:48 – 11:16:09	1400'	Quick cal OK, no full cal required
11:56:40	1000'	
12:01:40 – 12:01:55	1300'	Quick cal OK, no full cal required
12:48:10	2400'	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B137

Date: 03/13/06

Operator: MAP

Page 1 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:20:51	50	0.06	170								Start Profile 1 from 5000'
09:21:48	10	0.06									4000'
09:22:52	900	0.12	198		170	200	1	100	200	12	3000'
09:23:49	500	0.17	307		230	200	1	4000	200	12	2000'
09:24:40	600	0.18	404		190	300	1	6000	200	12	End of P1 @ 1300'
09:26:00	600	0.17	547		100	300	1	6000	200	12	Start Run 1 @ 1300
09:28:00	630	0.18	671		150	350	1	6500	200	12	
09:30:00	800	0.16	850		140	325	1	6400	400	12	
09:32:00	780	0.18	990		120	450	1	12700	400	12	
09:34:00	930	0.19	1195		100	400	1	13200	200	12	
09:36:00	460	0.15	1613		25	250	1	800	200	12	
09:37:45											End of Run 1
09:39:49											Start Run 2 @ 2400'
09:40:00	600	0.17	2400		140	75	12				
09:42:00	400	0.17	2544								
09:44:00	20	0.06	2613								
09:46:00	20	0.06	2617								
09:48:00	50	0.06	2643								
09:50:00	90	0.06									
09:52:00	90	0.06									
09:52:18											End of Run 2
09:55:51											Start Run 3 @ 2400'
09:56:00	100	0.06									
09:58:00	80	0.06									
10:00:00	75	0.06									
10:02:00	30	0.06	2674								
10:03:13											End of Run 3 Start P3
10:03:49	630	0.17	2785		290	175	1				2000'
10:04:50											End of P2 Start Run 4 @ 1300'
10:05:00	430	0.12	2954		90	150	1				
10:07:00	380	0.14	3187		80	175	1				
10:09:00	325	0.16	3568		40	100	1				
10:11:00	400	0.15	4082		65	225	1				
10:13:17											End of Run 4

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B137

Date: 03/13/06

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:15:12											Start Run 5 @ 1300'
10:16:00	1000	0.19	5252		50	400	1	1500	400	12	
10:18:00			Crash								FIFO exceed + program hang
10:22:00	900	0.22	165		185	350	1	8000	400	12	
10:22:36											End of Run 5 Start Profile 3
10:23:42											End of P3 Start Run 6 @ 2400'
10:24:00	600	0.20	600		630	150	1				
10:26:00	800	0.20	644		300	100	1				
10:28:00	45	0.20	700								
10:30:00	65	0.20	706								
10:32:00	70	0.20	706								
10:34:00	90	0.06									
10:35:06											End of Run 6
10:38:05											Start Run 7 @ 2400'
10:39:00	100	0.06									
10:41:00	100	0.06									
10:43:00	70	0.06									
10:45:08											End of Run 7 Start P4
10:46:48											End of P4 Start Run 8 @ 1300'
10:47:00	650	0.06	915		335	175	1				
10:49:00	460	0.15	1281		400	300	1	400	200	12	
10:50:50											End of Run 8
10:51:51											Start Run 9 @ 1300'
10:52:00	500	0.22	1966		195	350	1	4000	400	12	
10:54:00	450	0.21	2240		245	300	1	1800	200	12	
10:56:00	340	0.13	2427		400	300	1	1000	200	12	
10:56:18											End Run 9 Start P5
10:57:34											End P5 Start Run 10 @ 2400'
10:58:00	360	0.10	2640		50	100	1				
11:00:00	310	0.10	2718		95	100	1				
11:02:00	45	0.10	Reboot								
11:04:00	50	0.10	0								
11:06:00	50	0.06									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B137

Date: 03/13/06

Operator: MAP

Page 3 of 5

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks	
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size		Habit
11:08:00	75	0.07	0			2			140			
11:08:11												End of Run 10
11:11:20												Start Run 11 @ 1800'
11:12:00	150	0.16	18			2	800	1	140	1000	1	
11:14:00	85	0.08	21			1	700	1	50	800	1	
11:14:58												End Run 11 start P6
11:15:45												End of P6 Start Run 12 @ 1300'
11:16:00	450	0.14	155			40	800	1	330	1200	1	
11:18:00	400	0.16	352			132	150	1				
11:20:00	200	0.16	565			144	150	1				
11:22:00	600	0.19	1057			260	300	1	150	2400	1	
11:23:14												End of Run 12
11:24:16												Start Run 13 @ 1300'
11:25:00	450	0.14	1456			340	200	1	25			
11:27:00	300	0.11	1740			270	275	1	650	400	12	
11:29:00	250	0.14	2011			300	325	1	510	200	12	End Run 13 Start Run 14 @ 1300'
11:31:00	335	0.14	2268			150	150	1	10			
11:33:00	125	0.07	2338									
11:35:00	100	0.08	2454			1						
11:37:00	130	0.11	2600			35	300	1	8			
11:39:00	275	0.21	2800			1	300	1	40	800	1	
11:41:00	140	0.07	2880						125	600	12	
11:43:00	200	0.08	2889			1	800	1	600	600	12	
11:45:00	200	0.12	2897			2	800	1	300	2000	1	
11:47:00	170	0.12	2904						25			
11:49:00	110	0.12	2908			1			180	400	12	
11:51:00	100	0.07										
11:51:39												End of Run 14
11:53:30												Start Run 15 @ 1000'
11:54:00	230	0.07										
11:56:00	200	0.08	2910			1			100	800	1	
11:58:00	350	0.14	2913			1	800	1	400	2000	1	
12:00:00	350	0.14	2928			3	800	1	500	3000	1	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B137

Date: 03/13/06

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:00:41											End Run 15
12:01:25											Start Run 16 @ 1300'
12:02:00	475	0.17	2935		15	800	1	900	3000	1	
12:04:00	400	0.13	2948		5	800	1	1500	2000	1	
12:06:00	240	0.11	3018		5	800	1	600	600	1	
12:08:00	300	0.13	3254		5	800	1	600	3600	1	
12:10:00	195	0.09	3282		3	800	1	200	400	12	
12:12:00	430	0.16	3392		230	575	1	1300	1800	1	
12:14:20											End of Run 16
12:15:17											Start Run 17 @ 1300'
12:16:00	850	0.17	4461		100	200	1	350	1200	1	
12:18:00	630	0.09	4912		50	100	1				
12:20:00	260	0.12	5080		10	75	1				
12:22:00	580	0.09	5229		12	800	1	16			
12:24:00	360	0.12	5316		15	800	1	430	1400	1	
12:26:00	610	0.16	5460		45	25	12	30			
12:28:00	750	0.14	5653		30	50	12	25	3400	1	
12:30:00	700	0.14	5883		20	400	1	180	600	1	
12:32:00	770	0.14	6180		85	400	1				
12:34:00	740	0.15	6448		60	450	1	200	400	12	
12:36:00	450	0.18	6892		20	400	1	100	600	1	
12:38:00	450	0.10	7099		30	25	12				
12:38:30											End of Run 17
12:40:37											Start Run 18 @ 1300'
12:41:00	410	0.09	7520		30	100	1	50	200	12	
12:42:32											End of Run 18
12:44:18											Start Run 19 @ 2300'
12:45:00	140	0.07	7825								
12:47:00	135	0.07	7826		2	300	1	260	300	1	
12:49:00	120	0.07									
12:51:00	140	0.07	7827								
12:53:00	135	0.07									
12:55:00	110	0.07									

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: ...B137.....

Date: 30/09/05

Campaign Name: CLOPAP.....

Operator: JIM HOPKINS

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
		PAN: Arcon pressure: 120 bar Coppersulphate \approx 11cm WAS: cylinder pressure \approx 75 bar.	
~08:55		TAKE OFF	
~09:00		FL100 NOx4 cal. Turn on WAS pump, 24V and compressed air. Time check - set to 2secs slower than HORACE. Descend to 5000ft	
09:20:49		Profile Descent to 1300 ft.	
09:26		Run1 @ 1300 ft. to WPA	
09:37		end of run. climb to 2400 ft.	
09:39:48		Run2 @ 2400 ft to WPB. In and out of cloud.	
09:44:00	1	filled on FF for 1 minute. 2400ft	3.32
09:47:16	2	FF for 30secs. 2400ft	3.28
		Turn back at same altitude	
09:55:45		Run3 @ 2400ft to WPA	
10:02:30	3	2400ft	3.27
		Profile descend to 1300ft over sea	
~10:04		Run4 @ 1300 ft	
10:09:21	4	1300ft	3.31
10:11:31	5	1300ft.	3.32
10:15:18		Run5 @ 1300ft to WPC	
10:22:31		end of run, profile climb 3. to 2400 ft.	
10:23:42		Run6 @ 2400 ft to WPD	

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: B137
 Date: 30/09/05
 Operator: Jim Hopkins

Campaign Name: CLOPAP

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
10:26:50	6	2400 ft	3.28
10:28:15	7	2400 ft	3.27
10:33:01	8	2400 ft	3.32
10:35:07		end of run, turn back @ same altitude	
10:38:03		Run 7 @ 2400 ft	
10:42:40	9	2400 ft	3.27
10:45:06		end of run 7, profile 4 descent to 1300 ft over sea	
10:50:01	10	1300 ft	?
10:51:52		Run 9 to WPE @ 1300 ft.	
10:56:17		end of run 9, profile 6 to 2400 ft.	
10:57:33		Run 10 @ 2400 ft from WPE to F	
11:00:48	11	2400 ft	3.28
11:02:06	12	2400 ft	3.28
11:05:45	13	2400 ft	3.28
11:08:09		End of Run 10. Descent to 1800 ft.	
11:11:20		Run 11 @ 1800 ft.	
11:12:58	14	1800 ft	3.29
11:14:00	15	1800 ft	3.29
11:14:58		end of run 11, profile 7 down to 1800 ft Run @ 1300 ft.	
11:16:20	33	1300 ft	3.3

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: ...B.137...

Date: 30/09/05

Campaign Name: ...CLOPAP.....

Operator: Jim Hopkins

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
11:17:55	34	1300 ft	3.30
11:20:03	35	1300 ft	3.31
11:23:14		End of run 12	
11:24:16		Run 13 @ 1300ft to WPG	
11:28:30		Run 14 @ 1300ft WPG to WPH	
11:30:32	36	1300ft	3.32
11:34:15	37	1300ft out of plume (out of cloud). - going in and out of cloud and boundary layers.	3.32
11:43:46	38	1300ft	3.32
11:51:38		end of run 14, descend to 1000ft.	
11:53:30		Run 15 @ 1000 ft	
11:57:55	39	1000ft	3.32
12:00:37		end of run 15, climb to 1300 ft.	
12:01:24		Run 16 @ 1300 ft	
12:06:15	40	1300 ft	3.32.
12:12:31	49	1300 ft	3.31
12:14:22		end of run 16,	
12:15:12		Run 17 @ 1300 ft from WPG to beyond WPA going into Thames estuary	
12:17:15	50	1300ft, between WPG and E.	3.31
12:23:15	51	1300ft, between WPE and C	3.32
12:31:01	52	1300ft, between WPC and A	3.31

Time	Bottle#	Comments	Final pressure
12:38:19	53	1300 ft in Thames Estuary	3.31
12:38:30		End of Run.	
12:40		Run 18 @ 1300 ft to WPA.	
12:42:30		end of run, climb to 2300 ft.	
12:44:14		Run 19 @ 2300 ft	
12:51:46	54	2300 ft Between WPA and B.	3.29
12:56:21		End of Run 19	
12:57:13		Run 20 @ 2300 ft WP B to D.	
13:00:59		End of Run 20	
13:01:56		Run 21 @ 2300 ft WP D to C	
13:06:45	55	2300 ft.	3.28.
13:12:56		End of 21 Ascend to FL100 for NO _x calcs.	
13:22:45	56	10,000 ft	3.01

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 137

Date: 30th September 2005

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2		n
Heimann		N	HVPS		N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25		N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100		N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		N			
FWVS		N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC		N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI		Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP		N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer		N
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters		y
“ JO1D	Y	y	AMS		Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS		N			
MARSS		N			
DEIMOS		N	<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES		N	NIR TDLAS		N
SWS		N	2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		y
SO2		Y	Formaldehyde		N
NOX		Y	ADA		n
CO		Y	CPI		N
ORAC		N	NOxy		y
PAN		y	PTRMS		y
PERCA		n	Bag Sampling		n
WAS		Y	Tube Sampling		N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B137

Date: 30th September 2005

Instruments

1. TWC not fitted
2. Flt Man short comms cable for laptop u/s

Aircraft

1. Airstairs u/s (hydraulic leak).

Satcom H Calls nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B137:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Not yet available. To follow in 2006
Cloud Physics Processing log	Post Flight processing log yet to be completed by FAAM/Met Office
CCN	Training flight with no data requested by the customer so no log available
Filters	No filters were used on this flight as the expected conditions were not found.
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy
PTrMS	No log is ever taken for PTrMS
Peroxide	No log is ever taken for Peroxide

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Forward Facing Cameras
4 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Professor Tom Choularton

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New plot, same times

Flight B137 12:43:29

Heading 51 deg Speed 204 knots Height 2.2kft Press 933mb

Lat 51.5N Long 1.3E Wind 12 ms-1/ 294 deg

Temp 16.34C Dewpoint 15.84C

From start to now

Current values			
---	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	45807	secs
---	TECO SO2	4.68	ppb
---	TECO NO	3.42	ppb
---	TECO NO2	3.17	ppb
---	TECO NOx	6.47	ppb